

COHESIONS FORMED BY MEANS OF HYPONYMS

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the study of the process of cohesion is manifested in the use of hyponyms. Hyponymy may be a semantic marvel and is showed within the association of a unit with a common word. The referent of a hyponym takes put within the expressive field of a nominative unit that covers categories of distinctive limit scales.

I. Introduction

Another common method of cohesion is manifested in the use of hyponyms. Hyponymy is a semantic phenomenon and is manifested in the connection of a unit with a common word. The referent of a hyponym takes place in the expressive field of a nominative unit that covers categories of different narrow scales. For example, cat "cat": animal, flute of instrument, chair of furniture (Chrystal 2008: 233).

Hyponymy pairs are an important source of lexical cohesion in speech communication. It is even obvious that their role in the structure of the text is no less than that of antonyms and synonyms. Hyponyms also play a special role in understanding the cases of word combinations. Because the metonymy formed on the basis of the relationship of hyponyms makes it possible to perceive individual types by means of categories. In the text, the relationship between the categorical unit and its subordinate part serves to form a cohesive bond. Compare:

1. The hooded pitta is a new species for the trip, and one that we would find only on the mainland. It is a ground bird that rummages through leaf litter on the forest floor looking for food. (NYT, October 4, 2017);

2. The simple muscular exertions involved in producing the familiar yes, yes, yes, he said, trigger an increase in endorphins, the brain chemicals known for their feel-good effect (NYT, September 13, 2018).

II. Literature review

The subject of the first of the quoted passages is about the hooded pitta, which belongs to a certain "species" and "ground birds". Readers of the text do not know in advance what kind of thing or animal the hooded pitta is, but they can speculate about the meaning of the phrase through the relationships in the text.

Likewise, in the following example, the term endorphins is a hyponym for the concept of brain chemicals. Based on this relationship alone, one can speculate about the meaning of the endorphin unit.

The relationship between a hyponym and its base unit has the character of metonymy, depending on the mention of this base word. The reader of the text transfers the properties of the base unit to the hyponym. The ease of understanding the base word encourages the understanding of the content of other categories and participates in the formation of text coherence.

III. Research methodology

The fact that metonymy is a conceptual phenomenon is reflected in the structure of various categories. J. Lakoff shows that a member of a certain category can take his place. For example, the category "nurse" is usually understood as "female nurse" (Lakoff 1987: 79-90).

In the text of English newspaper reports, it is common for the base unit to refer to the hyponym. Compare:

Under the kidney transplant proposal, younger patients would get the best organs. (WP, February 24), 2017f;

A federal regulation that allows automakers to choose what kind of seat belts to install in minivans does not protect the companies from being sued if they choose one that is less safe, the Supreme Court ruled Wednesday (WP, February 24, 2017).

IV. Analysis and results

The referent of the units "organs" and "kidney" in the first sentence are mutually compatible. The referent of the elements "companies" and "automakers" in the next sentence is also matching. In other words, the lexical units "automakers" and "companies" entering the metonymic relation "concept in place of another concept" form a cohesive bond of text parts based on the same relation. We will try to describe these relationships in a diagram:

Figure. Cohesion of the basic unit and hyponym

It is clear from the drawing that two different forms enter into a relationship of hyponymy. The concept activated by the hyponym is compatible with the concept represented by the base unit. The reason for this is the narrowing of the meaning of the base unit. The fact that different forms point to a single concept creates a unique cohesion without words.

It is worth saying that the mentioned metonymic relationship has a two-way direction, that is, just as a base word is used in place of a hyponym, a hyponym can also replace a base unit.

Conclusions. So, the concepts that the hyponym and the basic unit mean are in a "part-whole" relationship, and the concept that the hyponym refers to is part of the corresponding concept of the basic unit as a separate part. Cohesion created by means of hyponyms has two forms. In the first one, the concepts of cohesion link hyponym and basic unity cover each other.

A hyponym is implied when the base unit is in use, because the properties of the first are transferred to the second. Secondly, the presence of a hyponym and its base source in a metonymic relationship "part and whole" allows them to exchange places. As a result, a hyponym and a base unit express a separate concept in a given text fragment and contribute to the formation of a cohesive bond.

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